

RECENT ADVANCES IN THE CHEMISTRY OF BITTER PRINCIPLES CONTAINING β -SUBSTITUTED FURAN RING*

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It is a great privilege to be invited to deliver the Acharya P. C. Ray Memorial Lecture for this year and I sincerely thank the Council of the Indian Chemical Society for this honour.

We are observing to-day the 99th birth anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra, our revered *guru* and the father of modern chemistry in India. This occasion is one of recollection of the greatness of a noble mind, whose foresight and single-minded devotion have done so much to elevate the status of chemical sciences in India, and to enrich our life, thoughts, industry and economy. It is a day for honouring ourselves by paying our humble tribute to the Acharya, who, like the ancient *rishis*, realized that salvation cannot be gained without knowledge and set himself a task, the magnitude of which was out of all proportions to his frail body. Like Bhagiratha, he brought sparkling water to the arid region of chemical research in India so that the posterity may reap a rich harvest.

With feelings of deep gratitude I recall my first meeting with Acharya P. C. Ray in May 1920. That was a turning point in my career. I had decided for various reasons to discontinue higher studies, but before acting upon this decision I sought his advice. He immediately asked me to abandon the idea and to join his household. This I did the next day.

I was then asked to help him and others in the laboratory till I got admission in the M.Sc. class. I was elated with the anticipation that I would be asked to perform research experiments. But I was assigned the unexpected duties of a head cleaner. Throughout the day my task was to clean up the laboratory equipment, glassware, tables, etc., rendered dirty by the seniors, to whom this arrangement was obviously most welcome but not to me. However, this state of affairs continued for 3-4 weeks, when I was entrusted with an additional duty. This consisted of the delicate and time-consuming operation of weighing out analytical samples. All the weighings of mine were used to be checked by a senior worker in the beginning to see if these were accurate and dependable. This dull routine continued till the M.Sc. classes opened when I felt a great relief. At that time I hardly realized the importance of this training, which in my later life proved extremely valuable. I wonder, what would be the reaction of a young chemist, if he is asked to-day to perform a similar work before he is assigned any research problem.

Acharya Ray was very regular in his habits and a strong disciplinarian in the laboratory, which he regularly attended every day in the week including Sunday. Three to four hours a day he spent in reading. In fact, his love for literature was only second to his love for chemistry. Even in his advanced age he kept up this habit and when his eyesight became defective, others had to read out to him the matter that he selected. I have often felt that study of classical literature refreshed his tired mind and body to a great extent.

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A serious illness in his childhood impaired Acharya Ray's health and necessitated his temporary withdrawal from school. This gave him a golden opportunity to study languages and literature, in which he was deeply interested from an early age. History and biography had a special fascination for him. Knight's *Half-hours with the Best Authors* introduced him to the works of Shakespeare who remained his favourite author till the last day of his life. In fact, during 1939-41, he wrote a series of 17 critical articles on what he called "The Shakespearian Puzzle". These were published in the *Calcutta Review*. His failing health, however, did not permit him to complete the series. His other favourite authors were Dickens, Fielding, Gibbon, Emerson, etc.

As a teacher he was most stimulating. When I was a student he used to give lectures on history of chemistry. The emphasis was more on history than on chemistry and very often he would digress to topics, which were neither history nor chemistry.

He was a hard task master but gave complete freedom to his competent research students to pursue their own lines of investigations and provided them with opportunities to develop their talents. "Do something new" he used to say. When success seemed to be remote or progress disappointingly slow, he would encourage us by saying that a chemist had to be more patient than the proverbial ass; and when one achieved success none would be happier than he.

He was always conscious of his ill-health which was accentuated by insomnia. He appreciated good health and physique, and once advised us to devote some time everyday to play. Taking this advice too literally, we, the then research workers, started a tennis club in which Dr. K. S. Krishnan also enlisted himself as a member. After about a month, he happened to notice our absence from the laboratory one afternoon. He immediately ordered voluntary liquidation of the club. We realized then that his idea on the subject was entirely different from that of ours.

Like all great men, he had his peculiarities. He was very particular about the money that he spent on himself, but not on private charities. In fact, we knew that he parted with the major portion of his monthly income in assisting the needy. But he denied himself the luxury of eating an orange when its price was more than one pice or so.

To Acharya Ray the idea that students should dabble in politics or become a tool in the hands of the politicians was most repugnant. In the early twenties when the political leaders had asked the immature student community to leave their studies and take part in the struggle for independence, Acharya Ray was shocked. He vehemently opposed this move, and predicted that its consequences would be most disastrous. I remember, one afternoon a well-known politician came to the Science College and appealed to him to come out of his laboratory along with his students and research workers. Acharya Ray refused. But the politician said that he would not move out of the Science College till Acharya Ray had agreed to his proposal. After his usual evening constitutional in the *maidan*, Acharya Ray found the gentleman still in his room. He was furious and after a sharp exchange of words the disappointed politician had to leave. Had the students heeded the advice of Acharya Ray at that time, the academic atmosphere, I believe, would have been much better than what it is to-day.

Soon after he had joined the Presidency College, he took a bold decision to create a chemical and pharmaceutical works with a view to utilizing the abundant raw materials available in Bengal and to providing employment to youngmen of the middle class. The difficulties were many, but his

grim determination and courage overcame them all one by one. I do not propose to go into the details of the early history of the Bengal Chemical which have been already narrated by Acharya Ray in his *Life and Experiences of a Bengali Chemist*. The inefficient and tiny lead chamber near Tollygunge that he purchased for Rs. 1,000/- has in course of time been replaced by modern and large sulphuric acid plants. The pharmaceuticals that he himself started preparing in his spare time in the backyard of his residence at 91 Upper Circular Road were then few. Now the Bengal Chemical & Pharmaceutical Works lists a large number of different products, and its activities have expanded in many directions.

Acharya P. C. Ray lived to the full the life that he wished to live and never deviated from the standards which he set before himself. Next year falls the birth centenary of this great son of India and I am confident that his pupils, friends and admirers will come forward to make the centenary a success.

The subject of my address to-day is "Recent Advances in the Chemistry of Bitter Principles containing β -Substituted Furan Ring". Before I proceed I should like to say that the natural bitter principles, to which I am going to refer, are, in fact, entirely of plant origin.

For purposes of chemical classification, which is rather arbitrary, substances containing nitrogen or sulphur, steroids, colouring matters, etc. are usually excluded from the list. Glycosides, though usually bitter, are often classified separately. In other words, bitter principles are those that contain carbon, hydrogen, and oxygen and belong generally to groups other than those mentioned above. They seldom possess structural features in common.

Bitter substances are not confined to specific botanical families although plants belonging to a few families are usually bitter. The degree of bitterness varies from one part of the plant to another and obviously depends on the localization of the active principles. Many bitter plants are avoided by human beings and animals. Some of these are poisonous. A few mildly bitter plants or their fruits are, however, used in culinary preparations, e.g., *Trichosanthes dioica*, *Momordica charantia*, *Azadirachta indica*. Hop is an ingredient in the preparation of beer.

The cause of bitterness can often be traced to one or more specific chemical constituents, the contents of which vary with the age of the plant, season, soil, and climatic conditions. No correlation between chemical structure and taste has yet been established. Further, the origin and the ultimate role of these substances in plants are still, in most cases, a matter of conjecture. Evidences showing that genes control the formation of bitter principles are, however, accumulating. For example, it has been demonstrated that biosynthesis of bitter principles in *Cucurbitaceae* is regulated by a single dominant gene.¹

Plants containing bitter constituents used to occupy a prominent place in ancient Eastern and Western systems of medicine. To these substances was ascribed a variety of curative properties. While later scientific investigations have, in most cases, failed to substantiate such claims, some of them, which are considered useful, specially as appetizers, have been incorporated into modern pharmacopœias. Many bitter herbs continue to be valued as household remedies, particularly in the East.

The pharmacology of the bitter substances has not received much attention; nor has our knowledge of the biochemical properties of such compounds advanced far. Biochemical investigations of bitter principles, if systematically pursued, can be expected to yield interesting results.

The causes of the sensation of bitterness are not known. The cells responsible for perception of the different tastes (such as sour, sweet, saline and bitter) are located in different areas of the tongue. Those cells that can evoke response in contact with a bitter substance are concentrated in the middle of the tongue.

It is not possible to determine the index of bitterness of a substance by chemical analysis or by means of any known instrument. The sensitive human tongue is the only apparatus that is employed for the assay. Bitterness is often expressed in relative terms by comparison with brucine in a concentration of 1 : 4, 800,000.³ The most bitter substance known to-day is amarogenetin (the active principle of *Svertia chirata*), which can be detected by its taste even at a dilution of 1 : 14 million.³

Further, the perceptiveness of this taste varies from person to person. For example, if 100 individuals are permitted to taste phenylthiourea, 70 will declare it as bitter, and to the remaining 30, it will appear tasteless. The impression of bitterness also depends on weather conditions and atmospheric pressure. Reduction of the ambient pressure reduces the sensation. Consequently in evaluating bitterness, both human and meteorological factors have to be borne in mind.

This fact reminds me of an amusing incident in our laboratory about the year 1924-25. One afternoon Acharya Ray entered the laboratory carrying a white powder on a saucer. He asked three research workers to taste the substance after assuring them that it was not a poison. One of the three declared it to be tasteless, another found it bitter, while to the third it was sweet. Amidst laughter Acharya Prafulla Chandra said that the powder was nothing but a mixture of fine sugar and quinine, which the ants in his dining room had refused to touch.

The memory of this incident has persisted so much in my mind that it has influenced to some extent the choice of the subject for to-day's lecture.

I have already mentioned that the bitterness of a substance is not associated with any specific structural feature of the molecule. A slight modification of structure may, however, bring about a profound change in taste characteristics. Thus, glucose is sweet, but its tri-acetate is bitter.

Cohn⁴ has pointed out that sometimes in a homologous series, the taste of the compounds gradually changes from sweet to bitter. For example, ethylene glycol is sweet but hexamethylene glycol is bitter. H. Rentschler and H. Tanner⁵ have shown that the bitterness of stored red wine can be traced to the formation of condensation products of acrolein (which is derived by enzymatic action from glycerine) and polyphenols (derived from anthocyanins and tannins present in wine). In fact, he succeeded in synthetically preparing a number of bitter substances by condensation of unsaturated aldehydes with various types of polyphenols. But it is not my intention to discuss synthetic bitter compounds, which are numerous and belong to widely different chemical groups.

Ngaione.—Many natural bitter principles have furan or modified furan units in them. A few of these contain the β -substituted furan moiety. The simplest member of the latter group is ngaione, which was found in the essential oil of *Myoporum laetum*, a plant endemic to Australia and New Zealand, by F. H. McDowall.⁶ A. J. Birch, R.A. Massy-Westropp and S. E. Wright⁷ obtained the same substance from *Myoporum acuminatum* along with 3-furoic acid. T. Kubota and T. Matsuura⁸ isolated ngaione and a related substance, myoporone ($C_{10}H_{22}O_3$), from *Myoporum boffinoides*. They also demonstrated that ngaione is the enantiomorph of *d*-ipomeamarone,

the toxic bitter principle of sweet potato infected by black rot fungus, *Ceratostomella fimbriata*. It is accompanied by batatic acid, ipomeanine and 3-furoic acid. The Japanese workers have fully established the structures of all these compounds, which are shown in Chart I.

CHART I

From *Myoporum* species.

Ngaione (·-·).

Myoporone (·-)

3-Furoic acid.

From black rot infected sweet potato.

Same formula

Ipomeamarone (·+)

Batatic acid.

Ipomeanine.

+ 3-Furoic acid.

The association of all these closely related furan compounds is interesting from the metabolic aspect. Dr. Matsuura has kindly informed me that of these compounds only ngaione, *d*- and *dl*-ipomeamarone are bitter. He believes that the bitterness of these compounds is associated with the tetrahydrofuran system as some synthetic compounds having the tetrahydrofuran nucleus are also bitter.

Columbin.—Most of the bitter compounds have, however, greater structural complexities. Columbin is one of the earliest substances of this group to engage the attention of the chemists. Discovered in the root of *Jatropha palmata* in 1830, it has been found associated with two isomeric and allied bitter principles, namely, chasmanthin $C_{20}H_{22}O_7$ and palmarin $C_{20}H_{22}O_7$, the structures of which have yet to be settled.

The chemical constitution of columbin has been investigated by many and in particular by Feist⁹, Wessely¹⁰, and Barton¹¹ and their co-workers. Columbin has the formula $C_{20}H_{22}O_6$. It does not contain a free carboxyl group, but mild treatment with alkali transforms it to an *iso*-compound. Both columbin and *isocolumbin* share some chemical properties. Thus, both behave like dilactone and furnish identical monomethyl ether and monoacetate, although the OH group is neither enolic nor phenolic. Both the substances part with one molecule of carbon dioxide on heating strongly and the resulting products are incapable of forming acetyl and methyl derivatives. It has been shown that breakdown of a lactone group furnishes the carbon dioxide while the second lactone group is not disturbed during decarboxylation.

Although columbin and isocolumbin are easily decarboxylated, the dihydro compounds, formed by controlled hydrogenation, are resistant to decarboxylation.

The IR spectra of the decarboxylated compounds show the presence of $\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated ketone. The reactions are explained on the assumption of a lactone system with a tertiary OH group in α -position to the lactonic carbonyl. Catalytic hydrogenation of both columbin and isocolumbin leads to octahydro derivatives, both of which contain a free carboxyl group, formed by hydrogenolysis.

Considerable information regarding the basic ring structure of columbin has been gathered by identifying the products of (a) zinc dust distillation, (b) oxidation, and (c) alkali fusion. The products are :

1. *o*-Cresol.
2. 1 : 2 : 5-Trimethylnaphthalene.
3. 1 : 2 : 3 : 4-Benzene-tetracarboxylic acid.
4. 1 : 2 : 3-Benzene-tricarboxylic acid.
5. 2-Methylterephthalic acid.
6. 2 : 4-Dimethylbenzoic acid.

Further, Barton and Elad¹² have isolated 1-methylnaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid by further degradation of octahydro-decarboxy-columbic acid, thus establishing the position of one of the lactone groups (Chart II).

Ozonolysis of dihydrocolumbin destroys the furan ring and furnishes formic acid and keto-acids having 17 and 18 carbon atoms. The formation of these compounds is explained on the assumption of a β -substituted furan ring in columbin.

CHART II

The presence of the furan ring was proved from nuclear magnetic resonance data and chemically confirmed by K. Kubota and T. Matsuura¹³ by the Alder-Rickert reaction¹⁴ leading to furan-3 : 4-dicarboxylic ester.

The structure of columbin has been definitely established by Barton and Elad¹² on the basis of the above and other data, and the isomerization of columbin to isocolumbin has been traced to epimerization at α -carbon atom of the second lactone ring. The proposed structure can explain the formation of the different degradation products in a satisfactory manner (Chart III).

The simpler decomposition products are formed from either ring A or ring B, or both.

CHART III

Marrubiin.—*Marrubium vulgare* is a herb of some repute, which has long been used as an expectorant, for correction of liver and gall bladder dysfunction, and for other ailments. The curative value of this herb has been traced to the presence of the diterpenoid bitter principle, marrubiin, $C_{20}H_{28}O_4$. The structure of this compound has been clarified mainly by W. Cocker and co-workers.¹⁵ Marrubiin is a doubly unsaturated lactone. It is easily transformed to the corresponding acid by alkali and to a tetrahydro derivative on hydrogenation. The only OH group present in the molecule is not acylable, but is smoothly eliminated under the influence of dehydrating agents. The resulting anhydromarrubiin has three double bonds. The fourth oxygen atom is inert. Spectroscopic evidence, NMR data, and colour reactions indicated the presence of a furan ring while the presence of a γ -lactonic system was confirmed by its IR spectrum.

The primary chromic acid oxidation product of marrubiin is a saturated dilactone in which the furan ring is absent. On treatment of this substance with alkali, a monocarboxylic acid is formed, which is resistant to esterification, but from which carbon dioxide can be easily eliminated.

This behaviour suggests that the carboxyl group is tertiary. This acid was eventually degraded to a known substance, previously prepared by L. Ruzicka and F. Lardon¹⁶ from ambrein, and thus it enabled W. Cocker and co-workers¹⁶ to advance the correct structural formula for marrubiin.

CHART IV

Nimbin.—The “nim” plant (*Azadirachta indica*, A. Juss.) occupies an important place in the Indian materia medica. All parts of the plant are bitter and reputed to possess antiseptic and other therapeutic properties. Consequently considerable attention has been given to the study of its constituents, which are many. The investigations have been carried out mainly by S. Siddiqui, S. Bhattacharya, C. Mitra, N. S. Narasimhan, P. Sengupta and their collaborators.¹⁷ The oil of the “nim” seeds has been found to contain :

- (1) A sulphur-containing amorphous lactone, called nimbidin.
- (2) Nimbin, m.p. 205°.
- (3) Nimbinin, $C_9H_{10}O_8$, m.p. 192°.
- (4) Nimbidiol, a liquid.

Nimbidin could be hydrolysed to a neutral crystalline compound (neonimbidin), a crystalline nimbidic acid, and an amorphous nimbidinic acid. Both nimbidin and sodium nimbidinate have been shown to stimulate uterine contraction.

The trunk and root-bark have been found to contain, among others, nimbin and two phenolic compounds, sugiol and nimbiol. The structure proposed for nimbiol by Sengupta *et al.*¹⁸ has been confirmed by recent syntheses. The "nim" blossom also contains a number of constituents including nimbin.

Mitra, Narasimhan and Sengupta and collaborators have made interesting contributions to our knowledge of the structure of nimbin, but to date the constitution has only been partially clarified. The molecular formula of nimbin, which is either $C_{30}H_{36}O_9$ or $C_{28}H_{34}O_9$, can only be settled when the structure is definitely formulated.

There is little doubt that nimbin contains a β -substituted furan ring and an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketonic system. In addition, there are one acetoxy and two methoxycarbonyl groups. Consequently eight oxygen functions out of nine are accounted for. The formation of a C_{28} -dibasic acid from nimbin indicates the possibility that nimbin may have some structural features common with limonin, obacunone, and swietenolide, all of which, like nimbin, afford the identical polyalkylnaphthalene on dehydrogenation.

The relative positions of the different oxygen functions with respect to the bicarbocyclic ring are not known yet. The study of this compound has presented many unforeseen difficulties, but it is hoped that a clear picture of the chemical constitution will emerge in the near future. Investigations up to date have indicated the presence of the following system, besides the β -furyl group, in nimbin.

Limonin.—Some 120 years ago, Bernay¹⁹ isolated limonin from citrus fruits. Since then it has been found to be of widespread occurrence in the genus *Citrus*. It can be easily isolated from citrus seed oil along with two related compounds, namely, obacunone and nomilin. Nomilin, $C_{28}H_{34}O_9$, is bitter but obacunone is not.

Limonin is a δ -dilactone of the formula $C_{28}H_{30}O_8$. The corresponding dibasic acid easily reverts to the parent compound. A keto group has been located in limonin and the ultraviolet, infrared, and proton magnetic resonance spectra suggested the presence of a furan ring. This has been confirmed by T. Kubota and T. Tokoroyama²⁰ through the Alder-Rickert reaction.

Moreover, alkali was found to break up the limonin molecule into two units, meronimonal ($C_{21}H_{28}O_6$) and furan-3-aldehyde ($C_5H_4O_2$) without loss of any carbon fragment. Six oxygen functions out of 8 are accounted for by one ketonic and the two lactonic groups and the furan ring. The other two oxygen atoms are assumed to be ethereal in nature. Hydrogenation of limonin first leads to tetrahydrolimonin having the saturated furan ring and then to hexahydrolimoninic acid by hydrogenolysis of one of the lactone groups. Drastic degradation of limonin by means of alkali, followed by selenium treatment of the products, results in 1:2:5-trimethylnaphthalene, suggesting the possibility that two 6-membered fused carbocyclic rings are present in limonin.

The constitution of limonin has very recently been fully elucidated by the brilliant work of Arigoni, Barton, Corey, Jeger, and collaborators²¹. The stereochemistry is entirely based on the X-ray investigations of J. M. Robertson and his co-workers²².

The structure of limonin is represented in Chart V. This formula can satisfactorily explain the numerous chemical data, which have accumulated since the isolation of the compound. Time does not permit me to present a detailed account, but those interested in the subject may refer to *Experientia*.²¹

CHART V

Obacunone ($C_{28}H_{30}O_7$) was first isolated by Y. Murayama and J. Takata²³ in 1928 from *Phlledendron amurense* Rupr. It is also present in citrus seed oil. Nomilin, the second bitter principle of citrus seed oil, is readily transformed to tasteless obacunone on treatment with acetic anhydride and pyridine. Alkaline hydrolysis of nomilin gives acetic acid and obacunoic acid. Nomilin is believed to be a dihydroacetoxy derivative of obacunone²⁴ and Kubota and co-workers²⁵ have shown that obacunone contains, besides a keto-group, two lactonic units (shown below) which are joined through a hydronaphthalene ring system. These observations support the tentative formulas proposed for nomilin and obacunone by Arigoni *et al.*²¹

Quite recently T. Chakrabartty and Asima Chatterjee²⁶ have investigated the constituents of *Swietenia macrophylla* King, previously reported by S. S. Guha Sircar and T. Chakrabartty²⁶. E. L. Hirst, T. Chakrabartty and collaborators²⁷ have shown that one of these called, swietenolide, $C_{27}H_{34}O_8$, contains one methoxycarbonyl, two hydroxyl, one keto, one lactone, three C-methyl, and a β -substituted furan ring. On catalytic hydrogenation this bitter principle takes up six hydrogen atoms, leading to saturation of the furan ring and simultaneous opening up of the lactone system, which is allylic to the furan. This behaviour is reminiscent of those of columbin

and limonin. Various degradative experiments, so far carried out, suggest the presence of the following units in swietenolide.

It must be stated, however, that swietenolide could only be isolated, following baryta treatment of the alcoholic extract of the seeds of the plant, and that the possibility of its being an artifact cannot be excluded.

Swietenolide is accompanied by a non-bitter principle, called swietenine, of the molecular formula C₃₂H₄₂O₉. The constitution of this substance has been examined by S. Ghosh, T. Chakrabartty and A. Chatterjee.²⁹ Mild alkaline hydrolysis of swietenine eliminates tiglic acid and the resulting product, which is isomeric with swietenolide, develops a bitter taste. A tertiary hydroxyl, a methoxyl group, five C-methyl, and a 6C-ring ketone have been found to be present in the molecule. Further, it has been found to contain an αβ-unsaturated δ-lactone unit, which can be opened up reversibly. Ehrlich's test, UV, IR, and proton magnetic resonance spectra support the presence of a β-monosubstituted furan ring, which is destroyed on ozonolysis. It affords 1:2:5-trimethylnaphthalene on selenium dehydrogenation besides an isopropyl-polyalkylnaphthalene. The experimental facts have been explained on the assumption of a tentative structure, which is related to that of limonin.

Tinosporin.—The latest member to join this bitter fraternity is tinosporin. A. Chatterjee and S. Ghosh³⁰ have studied the structure of this active principle of *Tinospora cordifolia* Miers, an important drug in Ayurvedic medicine. The analytical data correspond to the formula C₂₀H₂₂O₆ or C₂₁H₂₄O₇. From UV, IR, and proton magnetic resonance data they conclude that tinosporin is a β-substituted furan with two δ-lactone groups. The lactonic function has been substantiated by titration. Moreover, it was found to contain two active hydrogen atoms (due to OH

groups) and one C-methyl group. Selenium dehydrogenation yielded, among other products, 1 : 2 : 5-trimethylnaphthalene. From these limited data tinosporin is believed to be a compound of the columbin type, but no tentative structure has been advanced.

Clerodin.—The leaves of *Clerodendrum infortunatum* (Family *Verbenaceae*) are used as a popular indigenous remedy for intestinal worms. H. N. Banerjee³¹ isolated from the plant a crystalline bitter principle, named clerodin, in 1936 and studied some of its chemical and biochemical properties. From analytical and other data, the formula proposed was $C_{19}H_{18}O_7$. Of the three oxygen atoms, two were reported to be present in an acetoxy residue and the third as a hydroxyl. But the work was not pursued further.

D. N. Chaudhury and P. C. Dutta³² re-examined the compound, and mainly on the basis of analytical and physical data advanced the formula $C_{23}H_{40}O_8$. They presumed the presence of one acetoxy and four hydroxyl groups in clerodin. They did not study the structure in detail, but believed it to belong to the steroid group.

A systematic investigation undertaken by A. K. Banerjee³³ proved that clerodin is homogeneous and can be sublimed unchanged in high vacuum. On the basis of analysis, molecular weight data, and acetyl estimation, the molecular formula $C_{24}H_{34}O_7$ seemed probable. X-ray analysis also supported this formula, but not those advanced by earlier workers.

Colour reactions, UV, and IR data of clerodin indicated the presence of a furan ring. Two acetoxy groups were located in clerodin. Although the IR spectrum showed the presence of OH group, clerodin could not be acetylated, nor could it be oxidized to a ketone. It is probable that this OH is a tertiary one. The sixth oxygen atom forms part of a furan ring, as already mentioned. Therefore the remaining oxygen function had to be accounted for.

Neither clerodin nor its deacetylated product formed oxime or semicarbazone, and the characteristic band for the $-CO-$ group was absent in the IR curve. Although the IR spectrum did not reveal the presence of a keto group in tetrahydroclerodin, yet it formed a crystalline dinitrophenylhydrazone under the usual conditions. This anomalous behaviour was explained by assuming the presence of a potential keto group in tetrahydroclerodin as part of a hemi-acetal or hemi-ketal system. In conformity with this assumption isomerization of tetrahydroclerodin was induced by hydrochloric acid, yielding a crystalline isotetrahydroclerodin. This compound gave the same DNPH as the parent compound. Further, it showed the presence of keto- group in the UV spectrum and responded to the expected iodoform reaction.

Desacetylclerodin is free from acetyl group as indicated by spectral evidence. Nevertheless, it furnished a molecule of acetic acid on drastic alkaline degradation. This fact can be satisfactorily explained by assuming the presence of a furan-hemi-ketal system which could be expected to break down by alkali as follows :

After accounting for the last oxygen function, which is part of the hemi-ketal system, a clue to the basic framework of the molecule was sought by the well-recognized process of selenium

dehydrogenation. From the products, 1:2:5-trimethylnaphthalene was isolated and identified. This fact suggests that clerodin may be related to the diterpenoid bitter principles, marrubiin and columbin.

The relative positions of the two acetoxy groups in clerodin were ascertained by periodic acid treatment of desacetylclerodin. The results indicated the presence of an α -glycol system. This was further supported by the chromic acid oxidation of the compound, leading to a yellow crystalline product, $C_{20}H_{28}O_5$, which behaved like a diosphenol. Hence clerodin should have the system, $-\text{CH}(\text{OAc})-\text{CH}(\text{OAc})-\text{CH} <$.

The IR-spectrum of clerodin also showed the presence of a *gem*-dimethyl group. This *gem*-dimethyl group has been located at C_1 by following a sequence of reactions, which is of general applicability to triterpenoids having a *gem*-dimethyl in position 1 and a hydroxyl at 2. Starting from desacetylclerodin, acetone was obtained as expected. Consequently the α -glycol system in desacetylclerodin should occupy positions 2 and 3.

Further, it seemed most likely that the hemi-ketal system of clerodin (and its derivatives) involves the furan unit, as is the case with marrubiin and columbin. Therefore desacetylclerodin may be represented by one of the two formulas :

A choice between the two formulas has been possible by observing the amount of periodic acid consumed by the molecule. The first structure should consume 1 mole of the per-acid, while the second one would demand 2 moles, because under the acidic experimental condition, the compound would behave like a 1:2:3-trihydroxy compound. Actually only one mole of periodic acid was used up. Hence the first structure was accepted.

The question regarding the contribution of the *gem*-dimethyl group towards the formation of 1:2:5-trimethylnaphthalene during the dehydrogenation of clerodin now arises. In other words, whether the methyl groups in 1 and 2 positions of this trimethylnaphthalene originate from the *gem*-dimethyl or the *gem*-dimethyl loses one methyl group leaving the second one in position 5. It is on record that selenium dehydrogenation of lupeol furnishes 1:2:5:6-tetramethylnaphthalene while the corresponding acetate gives 1:2:5-trimethylnaphthalene.

Since clerodin is a 2-acetoxy compound, we may, by analogy with lupeol acetate, assume that the methyl groups in positions 1 and 2 do not originate from the *gem*-dimethyl. One of them should therefore be derived from an angular methyl group in position 12 or 13. Clerodin is consequently formulated as

Both these formulas are in agreement with the entire chemical behaviour of clerodin.

These are the principal β -substituted furan compounds of plant origin that have been investigated fully or to a significant extent. The only common characteristic among them, besides the furan unit, is their bitter taste, which is, however, not associated with the presence of the furan ring.

I should like to emphasize that the relationship between taste and structure is still very obscure, although empirical generalization is possible within a narrow range. Many instances are known where the entry of a simple substituent in an organic molecule profoundly changes its taste characteristics. I have already referred to glucose and its acetate. Another convenient example is the acid acetic acid which develops a sweet taste when an amino-group enters the α -position. In the case of clerodin, the bitter taste persists even when the furan ring is reduced or the hydrogenated product is isomerized. Removal of the acetyl groups renders the substance tasteless. On the other hand, mildly bitter nimbin, when deacetylated, becomes strongly bitter.

Laserpitin, the bitter principle of *Laserpitium latifolium*, is an angelic ester; the substance loses its bitterness when this ester group is hydrolysed. On the other hand, tasteless swietenine, which is a tiglic ester, is transformed into a bitter substance on elimination of the tiglic acid residue. The contribution of acidic residues towards the development of bitter taste is therefore anomalous. It would, I think, be an interesting study to see how far the taste characteristics of a compound are altered by the removal or introduction of simple substituents.

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